

APPENDIX

Figure 9 illustrates the route structures in one of the synthetic sectors used for benchmarking.

Fig. 9. One of the synthetic sectors used in the benchmarking.

We provide a full list of models included in our benchmarking experiments in table I.

TABLE I

THE MODELS USED IN THE BENCHMARKING EXPERIMENTS AND WHETHER THEY SUPPORT EXTENDED REASONING OR THINKING MODES.

WHERE NOT STATED, MODEL VERSIONS USED WERE THE LATEST AVAILABLE MODELS ON OPENROUTER AS OF 12TH AUGUST 2025.

PRICING DATA REFLECTS THE *average* COST PER MILLION OUTPUT TOKENS ON THE OPENROUTER PLATFORM AS OF 12TH AUGUST 2025.

Model	Reasoning	\$/M Output Tokens
qwen-3-8b-it [33]	✓	0.138
mistral-small-3.2-24b-instruct-2506 [34]	–	0.20
llama-3.3-70b-it [35]	–	0.23
gpt-oss-20b [36]	✓	0.28
gemma-3-12b-it [37]	–	0.33
gemini-2.5-flash-lite-preview-06-17 [38]	✓	0.40
gpt-oss-120b [36]	✓	0.48
llama-3.1-405b-it [39]	–	2.51
deepseek-r1-0528 [40]	✓	2.55
kimi-k2 [41]	–	2.58
gpt-4.1-2025-04-14 [42]	–	8.0
o3 [43]	✓	8.0
gpt-5 [44]	✓	10.0
gemini-2.5-pro [45]	✓	12.50

In Tables II, III, IV and V we present the benchmarking results for the varying scenario traffic volume, length, sector complexity, and interaction number benchmarks, respectively.

Figure 11 summarises the controllability benchmark: box plots of the number of interactions each model generates at different targets, revealing systematic under- and over-generation. While o3 stays close to the targets in all settings, Gemini-2.5-Pro struggles with higher targets. Most models increase conflicts as the target increases, but do not reliably match the requested counts, indicating limited fine-grained control.

Figure 10 compares the overall skill level across the four benchmarks (computed as the sum of the normalised skills) against inference cost. The dotted red line represents the Pareto front. It is particularly interesting to observe the GPT-oss models achieve close to optimal scores at a fraction of the cost.

A. Case Study: High-Volume Scenario Generation ($N = 30$)

We present two Gemini-2.5-Pro outputs on the $N = 30$ traffic-volume benchmark (Figures 12a and 12b). The model is successful in Figure 12a and fails in Figure 12b, illustrating both the complexity of the task and, in the success case, the strategy employed by a reasoning-capable model.

In this section, we study the effect of giving models access to feedback on their attempts. We evaluate the four best-performing models from the varying number of aircraft benchmark (excluding GPT-5, which saturated the benchmark). In Table VI, we present their performance *after receiving feedback about their performance*. Using our automated verifier, we give each model five scored attempts to produce a non-interacting scenario. Specifically, we inform the model which aircraft are involved in interactions when it fails to create a non-interacting scenario. We observe that **in all cases, the models achieve perfect performance after a single round of feedback**.

Furthermore, it is interesting to note that the models achieve this by making *significant* changes to the scenario. In all cases, they modify the parameters of multiple aircraft, not just those involved in the highlighted interactions.

In Figure 13 we show that the method is able to accurately generate all three types of pairwise interactions.

Fig. 11. Benchmarking LLM performance with varying numbers of input conflicts. o3 and GPT-5 saturate the metric, and therefore we include their individual data points to maintain readability.

(a) Gemini-2.5-Pro **solving** the $N = 30$ benchmark: there are no interactions in this scenario. It devises a strategy where aircraft are systematically spawned in sequences along the same route, thus avoiding conflicts. Sequences of aircraft on intersecting routes avoid one another by careful selection of spawn times. (Snapshots shown every two time units for convenience).

(b) Gemini-2.5-Pro **failing to solve** an $N = 30$ benchmark: there are three interactions in this scenario. At time $t = 10, 11$ aircraft 11 interacts with aircraft 21 and 22 respectively, in a head-on manner. Similarly, at $t = 11$, aircraft 12 interacts with aircraft 22. Notice that, similar to Figure 12a, the model has attempted to thread sequences of aircraft along the same route one-by-one. In this case, it has miscalculated the time at which aircraft 21 would reach the end of its route. (Snapshots shown every two time units for convenience).

Fig. 12. Gemini-2.5-Pro performance on the $N = 30$ benchmark: success (left) and failure (right).

TABLE III

BENCHMARKING RESULTS FOR VARYING SCENARIO LENGTH. VALUES QUOTED ARE THE AVERAGE NUMBER OF UNIQUE INTERACTING PAIRS OF AIRCRAFT COMPUTED ACROSS 10 GENERATED SCENARIOS ON 10 SYNTHETIC SECTORS. OPTIMAL BEHAVIOUR (MARKED WITH A CHECKMARK) IS ZERO INTERACTING PAIRS.

Scenario Length	12	15	18	21	24
random baseline	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.2
qwen3-8b-it	1.3	1.2	1.0	1.7	1.2
kimi-k2	1.0	1.6	1.0	0.4	0.9
llama-3.1-405b-it	1.3	0.9	1.3	0.7	0.9
gemma-3-12b-it	0.6	0.9	0.9	1.2	0.6
mistral-small-3.2-24b-instruct-2506	0.6	1.0	0.7	1.0	0.5
gemini-2.5-flash-lite-preview-06-17	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2
gpt-4.1-2025-04-14	✓	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1
llama-3.3-70b-it	0.8	0.4	0.9	0.3	0.1
gemini-2.5-pro	✓	✓	✓	✓	0.1
deepseek-r1-0528	0.2	✓	0.1	✓	✓
gpt-oss-20b	0.1	✓	✓	0.1	✓
o3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
gpt-oss-120b	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
gpt-5-low	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
gpt-5-high	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

(a) Cross-paths interaction

(b) Head-on interaction.

(c) Catch-up interaction: AC2 overtakes AC1 due to differing ground speeds (denoted GXXX).

Fig. 13. Examples of fine-grained scenario controllability using AirTrafficGen.

TABLE IV

BENCHMARKING RESULTS FOR INCREASING SECTOR COMPLEXITY. VALUES QUOTED ARE THE AVERAGE NUMBER OF UNIQUE INTERACTING PAIRS OF AIRCRAFT COMPUTED ACROSS 10 GENERATED SCENARIOS ON 10 SYNTHETIC SECTORS. OPTIMAL BEHAVIOUR (MARKED WITH A CHECKMARK) IS ZERO INTERACTING PAIRS.

Sector Route Intersections	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
random	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.3	2.3	2.7	2.5	2.7	2.9	2.7	3.1
qwen3-8b-it	1.3	1.6	1.2	2.3	1.4	2.4	2.3	2.6	3.8	3.5	3.1
kimi-k2	1.2	1.6	0.9	1.4	1.7	2.0	2.0	1.4	2.1	2.2	3.0
mistral-small-3.2-24b-instruct-2506	1.0	0.7	1.1	1.4	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.3	1.8	2.9
gemma-3-12b-it	1.2	1.2	0.8	1.7	0.9	1.5	1.1	2.1	2.3	2.8	2.8
llama-3.1-405b-it	0.5	1.2	0.6	1.0	0.9	1.9	1.8	1.8	1.6	1.9	2.4
deepseek-r1-0528	✓	✓	0.1	0.6	0.8	0.7	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.5	1.7
gemini-2.5-flash-lite-preview-06-17	0.6	0.9	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.9	0.9	1.2	1.0	1.3	1.5
llama-3.3-70b-it	1.0	0.5	0.4	1.0	1.2	0.8	1.2	0.7	1.7	1.5	1.2
gpt-4.1-2025-04-14	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.7	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.7	0.8
gemini-2.5-pro	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	0.1	0.5	0.1	✓
gpt-oss-20b	✓	✓	✓	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	✓	0.1	✓	✓
o3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
gpt-oss-120b	✓	✓	✓	0.2	✓	0.1	✓	✓	0.2	0.3	✓
gpt-5-low	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	0.1	✓	✓
gpt-5-high	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	0.1	✓

TABLE V

BENCHMARKING RESULTS FOR INCREASING NUMBER OF INPUT CONFLICTS. VALUES QUOTED ARE THE MEAN ABSOLUTE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE NUMBER OF GENERATED INTERACTING PAIRS OF AIRCRAFT AND THE INPUT NUMBER. THIS AVERAGE IS COMPUTED ACROSS 10 GENERATED SCENARIOS ON 10 SYNTHETIC SECTORS. CHECKMARKS DENOTE PERFECT PERFORMANCE ACROSS ALL 10 SYNTHETIC SECTORS (A MEAN ABSOLUTE DIFFERENCE OF ZERO).

Number of Interactions	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
random baseline	1.95	1.55	1.49	1.92	2.58
llama-3.3-70b-it	1.30	1.30	1.70	2.20	4.20
deepseek-r1-0528	0.30	0.60	0.90	1.20	3.90
openai/gpt-oss-20b	✓	✓	1.10	3.00	3.80
gpt-4.1-2025-04-14	0.50	2.20	1.40	2.40	3.40
gemini-2.5-flash-lite-preview-06-17	1.90	2.00	3.30	1.20	3.00
gemma-3-12b-it	1.20	1.20	1.60	2.20	2.90
llama-3.1-405b-it	0.90	1.50	2.20	2.10	2.80
qwen3-8b-it	1.80	1.90	2.10	2.20	2.80
mistral-small-3.2-24b-instruct-2506	0.90	1.50	1.50	1.90	2.50
kimi-k2	0.90	1.20	1.30	2.20	1.90
gemini-2.5-pro	✓	0.10	0.60	1.50	1.70
openai/gpt-oss-120b	✓	0.50	0.50	1.60	0.80
o3	✓	✓	✓	0.40	0.30
gpt-5-high	✓	✓	0.10	0.20	0.20
gpt-5-low	✓	✓	0.10	✓	0.10

TABLE VI

BENCHMARKING RESULTS FOR VARYING NUMBERS OF AIRCRAFT. ON A SUBSET OF THE BENCHMARK, WE COMPARE THE PERFORMANCE OF FIVE MODELS TO THEIR PERFORMANCE AFTER BEING GIVEN ACCESS TO AUTOMATED VERIFICATION OF THEIR SOLUTIONS AND UP TO FIVE OPPORTUNITIES TO CORRECT ANY ERRORS. VALUES QUOTED ARE THE AVERAGE NUMBER OF UNIQUE INTERACTING PAIRS OF AIRCRAFT COMPUTED ACROSS 10 GENERATED SCENARIOS ON 10 SYNTHETIC SECTORS. OPTIMAL BEHAVIOUR (MARKED WITH A CHECKMARK) IS ZERO INTERACTING PAIRS. ALL MODELS IN ALL CASES NEEDED ONLY ONE ATTEMPT TO CORRECT ALL THEIR MISTAKES.

Number of aircraft With Feedback	10		15		20		25		30	
	No	Yes								
gemini-2.5-pro	0.1	✓	0.6	✓	3.2	✓	0.3	✓	0.9	✓
gpt-oss-20b	0.1	✓	0.1	✓	0.7	✓	1.0	✓	0.2	✓
o3	✓	✓	✓	✓	0.2	✓	0.2	✓	✓	✓
gpt-oss-120b	0.2	✓	✓	✓	0.1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓